

Sustainable Supervisory Indices For Combating Corruption as Correlates of Quality School Governance in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: *The study investigated sustainable supervisory indices for combating corruption as correlates for quality school governance. The study area was Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State Nigeria. Two null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. The ex- post facto design was adopted for the study. Census sampling technique was used to sample all the eighty-one (81) principals for the study. Sustainable Supervisory Indices for Combating Corruption and School Governance Questionnaire (SSICCQSGQ) was the instrument used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.78 which was established using Cronbach alpha reliability method. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson's product moment correlation statistics, and the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a high positive correlation between classroom observation and demonstration techniques and school governance in public secondary schools in Calabar education zone of Cross River State. Based on the findings, the conclusion was drawn and it was recommended among others that government should provide opportunity for principals to attend conferences, workshops, seminars and colloquiums on sustainable supervisory indices at least once a year both nationally and internationally for more acquisition of skills and knowledge for combating corruption and foster effective school governance in order to keep them at par with their foreign counterparts.*

Keywords: *Sustainable, Supervisory indices, Combating corruption, School governance, Corruption*

Introduction

Governance in the world generally has similar roles and responsibilities. Good governance implies that certain responsibilities, practices, policies, and procedures be exercised by an institution to provide strategic direction and to ensure objectives are achieved within a time frame and that resources are managed or utilized responsibly and accountable. Good governance practices enable schools to manage their resources so that they can deliver quality education. Apart from the federal government, each state also has certain regulations which must be adhered by all schools. Within each state there are districts, and these districts have boards over them to regulate how schools within their jurisdiction should function. Again, it is these boards that cause public school governance to either succeed or fail. These boards, constantly assess, improve, maintain, and regulate the institutions within their districts.

Quality school governance promotes a more democratic and responsive system of school management, including efficient utilization of resources, improved participation of all stakeholders (teachers, students, parents, and school management) in the development of school policies, rules, plans, and code of conduct. School governance is essential to promote a culture in which the ultimate expectation for future generations is that the children will eventually be able to maintain and improve the society. The most authoritative governing force is the school administrators. They regulate the basics of how schools should operate and educate the learners. If schools must be effectively governed, it must be done in a manner that corruption will not be guaranteed. It was expected that those saddled with the responsibilities to managed schools, provide all the needed support for effective teaching and learning.

It is, however, very sad to observe that the level of corruption in Nigerian secondary schools' governance can no longer allow school administrators to prepare students for useful living in the society and for further studies into tertiary institutions. Contextually, corruption in this paper refers to an absurd or deviant disposition of school authority which violates the ethical standards. The prevalence of corruption in secondary school is viewed to negate the core values of educational philosophy at this level. It is potent cancer that has mercilessly eaten Nigerian secondary education to a state of stupor Nwangwu (2018). The Concise Oxford English Dictionary (Words worth Reference) views corruption as putridity, taint, debasement, spoliation,

impurity, perversion, bribery, dishonesty, venality, rottenness, and immorality. This definition is all-encompassing as it views everything that is evil as corruption.

Lack of principals' observational supervision on quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school organisational innovation, and learning outcome is what most stakeholders agitate for at the moment. Unfortunately, most school administrators cannot supervise and conduct teacher performance evaluations based on regular attendance. They do not examine how teachers start and end classes with instructional materials, relate to students according to their psychological needs, use a variety of teaching and learning methods, involve all students in the learning process, ensure coordination between students and parents. Some school administrators cannot encourage demonstration supervision among teachers and teachers, and between teachers and students as a result of corrupt practices in the school. They hardly pay attention to school and student cleanliness and are rarely found engaging in co-curricular activities. They also appear to be ineffective in keeping transparent maintenance of the accounting system. They cannot maintain updated information on the school and cannot also streamline the duties and responsibilities of the teachers. They lack skills to generate essential resources for the school from local and other sources through the active participation of stakeholders. They do not also disclose information on the resources generated and how much of those resources generated are used for teaching.

It has been observed that some principals cannot manage and maintain the school building, toilets, drinking water, and furniture. In fact, they are the personification of corruption. With their loaded corrupt tendencies, they cannot keep a record of resources generated from donors and local agencies, keep a record of the property of the school (mobile and immobile), conduct income-generating activities, monitor the management of school fund, library, and other basic facilities, monitor classroom conditions and seating arrangements for students, monitor the arrival and management of students. They cannot monitor the execution of activities under the annual plan. Corrupt governance in the secondary school system has degenerated into child-unfriendly teaching among the teachers, poor use of various methods of teaching, inappropriate use of corporal punishment to mention but a few.

Corrupt free school governance adopts supervision to ensure that the school's core values are put into consideration by the principal. It ensures that the vision, mission and the objectives of the school take strategic direction. It takes into account, the individual personalities, interests of key stakeholders, current students and parents, former students, prospective students and parents, affiliates (e.g., religious association), government funders, benefactors, staff, local community, and other relevant groups. Usman, Bushra, and Talat (2015) found that the results obtained from a correlation and regression analyses revealed that supervision practices of principals related to staff development are indeed helpful in combating corruption and attaining better performance of teachers and their overall growth. Further, it was also found that there is much difference between staff development practices of male and female school principals. On the other hand, the results of data analysis also found a significant difference between work performance and growth of male and female school teachers. Greg (2013) also found that roughly one-fifth of agriculture teachers were observed teaching by their supervisor during an entire academic year. In addition, more than half of the teachers had participated in a pre-observation conference, and about one third had participated in a post-observation conference with their supervisor. It was concluded that a significant number of agriculture teachers in Iowa were neither supervised nor evaluated during a complete academic year. Similarly, Yusuf, Aminu, and Ibrahim (2015) submitted that school principals possess greater information about the school system and about instructional and management strategies that can strengthen the teachers' capacity to cope with classroom problems and thereby ensure adequate and effective learning on the part of the students. Usman (2015) found that regular instructional supervision using robust supervision strategies like checking of students' notebooks, classroom visitation/inspection by school administrators, demonstration techniques, checking teachers' lesson plan/notes and inspection of teachers record keeping have a significant correlation with teachers' performance and academic achievement of students in Secondary Schools. Namunga (2017) established that there was a significant relationship between supervision of instructional practices and combating corrupt practices at p=

0.005 level of significance. Therefore, it was concluded that supervision of instructional practices significantly influenced quality teaching and learning in secondary schools.

Oyewole and Alonge (2013) indicated a significant relationship between instructional, supervisory role performance of principals and the motivation of their teachers. A significant positive relationship was found between the experience of principals in performing their instructional, supervisory roles and the motivation of their teachers. There was also a significant relationship between instructional, supervisory role performance of principals of large schools and small schools and the motivation of their teachers. Findings from the study of Simbano (2015) revealed that the majority of the teachers had positive attitudes towards supervision. Findings indicated that the majority of head teachers strongly agreed that supervision benefits teachers on improving their teaching within the classroom and reduces lesson absence by teachers. The major challenges facing head teachers in supervisory practices were overload work by teachers, and lack of certain teaching/learning materials averts effective instructional supervision process.

Statement of the problem

The persistent corruption and sympathetic state of school governance leading to the poor academic performance of secondary school students in Calabar education zone is a cause of concern to educational stakeholders. This seems to indicate that most school administrators lack adequate knowledge and supervisory skills to solve the perennial problem of school corruption. This nurtures all sorts of malpractices and makes it difficult for secondary schools in Nigeria to respond to the perceived needs of producing graduates who could make useful living in the society, and as well further to higher education. The principals in the State seem to spend more of their statutory hours on other administrative duties to the detriment of supervision.

In attempting to address this issue, the researchers believe that to eliminate corrupt practices at the secondary level, the right kinds of principals that will demonstrate good school governance are needed. The researchers also suspect that employing observational and demonstration supervisory techniques that will inspire teachers and students with a desire for self-improvement, may be necessary also to raise morally upright, and well-adjusted individuals who should be able to think independently, rationally, appreciate the dignity of labour and achieve excellence which are all necessary to channel the nation to the envisaged transformation.

It is in the light of this unpleasant situation and the need to provide solutions that this study was set out to investigate the influence of principals' supervisory techniques in school governance and attainment of anti-corruption education in secondary schools in Calabar Education zone of Cross River State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain sustainable supervisory indices for combating corruption as correlates of quality school governance. Specifically, the study sought to examine the relationship between:

1. Principals' classroom observation technique and quality school governance.
2. Principals' demonstration technique and quality school governance

Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' classroom observation techniques and quality school governance.
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' demonstration techniques and quality school governance.

Methods

The study adopted a correlation design. This design was considered more appropriate because it was the intent of the study to investigate the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The study population comprised all the 81 principals in Calabar Education. Census sampling technique was used in selecting the entire population of 81 principals for the study.

The researchers developed an instrument titled: Sustainable Supervisory Indices for Combating Corruption and Quality School Governance Questionnaire (SSICCCQSGQ) which was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts who are lecturers; two in the Department of Educational Administration and the other in Measurement and Evaluation all from Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, Calabar. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha method. This yielded coefficients of 0.78 and 0.82 respectively for the two independent variables of the study. With these values, the instrument was considered internally consistent for measurement.

The administration of the instruments was carried out by the researchers through direct administration method. A total of 81 questionnaires were distributed, and 80 copies of the questionnaire were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating a 98 percent return. Pearson product moment correlation statistics were used for data analysis and hypothesis test. The coefficient (r) and the strength of the relationship were interpreted using the interpretation of correlation coefficient as shown: 0.80 and above for high, 0.30 to 0.79 for moderate and 0.29 and below for low respectively. In testing the null hypotheses, if r-calculated is equal to or greater than r-critical at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is insignificant, but if otherwise, it is significant.

Results

Hypothesis One

Principals’ observational technique in combating corruption does not significantly relate to quality school governance. The data for this hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation statistics. The results of the analysis were as presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between principals’ observational technique in combating corruption and quality school governance (N = 81)

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	r-cal.	p-val.
Principals’ observational supervision	10.95	3.483	-	-
Instructional supervision	12.00	2.492	.314	.000
Organisational innovation	12.24	2.741	.394	.000
Learning outcome	11.63	3.683	.478	.001

* Significant at $p < .05$, critical $r = .217$, $df = 79$

The result presented in Table 1, showed that for principals’ observational technique in combating corruption and instructional supervision ($r = .314^*$, $p < .05$), for principals’ observational technique in combating corruption and organisational innovation ($r = .394^*$, $p < .05$) and for principals’ observational technique and learning outcome ($r = .478^*$, $p < .05$). A cursory look at the calculated R-values shows that; .314, .394, and .478 are all greater than the critical r-value of .217 for the three dimensions respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected implying that; there is a significant relationship between principals’ observational technique in combating corruption and quality school governance for the three dimensions assessed.

Hypothesis two

Principals’ demonstration technique in combating corruption does not significantly relate to quality school governance. The data for this hypothesis was analysed using Pearson product moment correlation statistics. The results of the analysis were as presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between principals’ demonstration technique in combating corruption and quality school governance (N = 81)

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	r-cal.	p-val.
Principals' demonstration technique	12.36	2.981		
Instructional supervision	12.00	2.492	.299*	.042
Organisational innovation	12.24	2.741	.916*	.000
Learning outcome	11.63	3.683	.335*	.034

* Significant at $p < .05$, critical $r = .217$, $df = 79$

The result presented in Table 2 showed that for principals' demonstration technique in combating corruption and instructional supervision ($r = .299^*$, $p < .05$), principals' demonstration technique in combating corruption and organisational innovation ($r = .916^*$, $p < .05$) and for principals' demonstration technique of combating corruption and learning outcome ($r = .335^*$, $p < .05$). A cursory look at the R-values shows that; .199, .916 and .135 are all greater than the critical r-value of .217 for the three dimensions respectively. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected implying that, there is a significant relationship between principals' demonstration technique for combating corruption and quality school governance for the three dimensions assessed.

Discussion of findings

The result of data analysis indicated that; there is a significant relationship between principals' observational technique in combating corruption and quality school governance for the three dimensions assessed in Calabar education zone of Cross River State. This implies that principals' regular observation of teachers' instructional delivery in the classroom in terms of mastery of the subject matter, application of teaching strategies and aids, classroom management, and organization among other have a positive influence on school governance hence combating corruption. This contradicts the finding of Akinwumi (2012) who reported that supervision has no significant impact on combating school corruption. This contradiction could be attributed to differences in demographic variables and in a geographical area. The finding of this study also revealed that there is a significant relationship between principals' demonstration techniques and school-based governance in secondary schools in Calabar education. This finding is supported by Sule, Arop, and Alade (2013) who reported that there was a significant influence of principals' classroom visitation/observation strategies in combating corruption for school quality governance

The findings of this study also established that; there is a significant relationship between principals' demonstration technique for combating corruption and quality school governance for the three dimensions assessed. Principals' demonstration or illustration of a concept provides the opportunity for teachers to discover new methods and ideas to be applied during instructional delivery in order to enhance their performance. Yusuf, Aminu, and Ibrahim (2015) submitted the principals possess greater information about the school system and about instructional and management strategies that can strengthen the teachers' capacity to cope with classroom problems and thereby ensure adequate and effective learning on the part of the students. Usman (2016) found that regular instructional supervision using robust supervision strategies like checking of students' notebooks, classroom visitation/inspection by school administrators, checking teachers' lesson plan/notes and inspection of teachers' record keeping have a significant correlation with teachers' performance and academic achievement of students in Secondary Schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there was a significant relationship between sustainable supervisory indices for combating corruption and quality school governance. Thus, regular observation of teachers and demonstration to teachers supervision, and provision of the necessary professional guidance has positive relationship with quality of school governance in terms of instructional supervision, organisational innovation, learning outcome, subject matters, presentation of lesson in a well-organized manner, effective classroom organization and control, participation in the school curricular activities, regularity and punctuality in the school, discipline, motivation and counselling of students among others.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- i. The government should provide an opportunity for principals to attend conferences, workshops, seminars and colloquiums on sustainable supervisory indices at least once a year both nationally and internationally for more acquisition of skills and knowledge for combating corruption through quality school governance and instructional supervision in order to keep them at par with their foreign counterparts.
- ii. Principals should endeavour to regularly observe teacher's classroom instructional delivery and provide professional guidance and assistance to them where necessary

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